

INTRODUCTION OF INNOVATIVE CREATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGY IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS OF GYNECOLOGY

Urinova Sharofat Akhtamovna¹

¹ Bukhara Medical Institute named after Abu Ali Ibn Sina

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ABSTRACT

In many international publications devoted to pedagogical technology, one can find such an understanding of it: "pedagogical technology is not just the use of technical means of teaching or computers; it is the identification of principles and the development of methods for optimizing the educational process by analyzing factors that increase educational efficiency, by designing and applying techniques and materials, as well as by evaluating the methods used" The essence of this approach lies in the idea of full controllability of the work of an institute or other educational institution.

Relevance: In many international publications devoted to pedagogical technology, one can find such an understanding of it: "pedagogical technology is not just the use of technical means of teaching or computers; it is the identification of principles and the development of methods for optimizing the educational process by analyzing factors that increase educational efficiency, by designing and applying techniques and materials, as well as by evaluating the methods used" The essence of this approach lies in the idea of full controllability of the work of an institute or other educational institution. According to the characteristics of the Japanese scientist and teacher T. Sakamoto, pedagogical technology is the introduction of a

systematic way of thinking into pedagogy, which can otherwise be called "systematization of education" The task of our research was to search for evidence of the productivity of creative technologies in the successful modernization of medical education. Science and practice need to solve this problem, but so far even the concept of "creative technology" is not a generally accepted and unambiguously understood concept. In the process of learning, technology is understood as the technological process of implementing educational activities, a model of interaction between participants in the educational process. Traditional pedagogical technology is "a set of psychological and pedagogical attitudes that determine the social set and layout of forms, methods, methods, teaching

methods, educational tools; it is the tools of the pedagogical process" (B. T. Likhachev). M. V. Clarin considers technology through a system: pedagogical technology is "the system totality and the order of functioning of all personal, instrumental and methodological means used to achieve pedagogical goals." Pedagogical science, in response to the demands of society and the state, is actively looking for ways to achieve high results. Hundreds of methods, techniques, pedagogical findings are described, but they do not provide a goal. The construction of the pedagogical process in accordance with a specific goal and the indispensable receipt of a positive result led to the discovery of such an algorithm as technology. The presence of a result is a component that does not cause doubts in the research community. But as the main characteristics of pedotechnology, scientists offer different grounds: consistency, integrativity, reproducibility, motivation, novelty, the possibility of repetition, adaptation in new conditions, etc. According to T. S. Anisimova, means of control are an obligatory component of educational technology, along with motivation, diagnostics, algorithmicity. N. V. Anikina believes that educational technology is a targeted application of a system of means aimed at and determining the receipt of specified characteristics of some educational phenomenon. Technologies can ensure the productivity of a mega-level, macro-level, micro-level education strategy. Many researchers understand technology as a didactic system (forms, methods, means of teaching algorithmically organized and having a very specific result in the implementation of the content of learning). V. P. Bespalko

considers technology to be the embodiment of the art of a teacher in pedagogical activity. The description of a new, creative process that accompanies pedagogical activity and transforms the teacher's material into the possibility of replication, transfer to other conditions with a given result is a creative technology. The word "techne" means art, that is, what the teacher owns. "Logos" in translation means teaching. That is, we can talk about technology as the art of teaching, pedagogical skill, where the learning process has become the unity of science and creativity, the art of the teacher. Technologies may not originate in the educational sector, but their skillful adaptation in education, the use of the experience of other industries, contribute to the enrichment of pedagogical science and educational practice. In technical systems, the experience of technologies has been formed, the development of which takes place in accordance with the laws of dialectics. In pedagogy, the effect of these laws is adapted through the intellectual and psychological characteristics of the teacher. However, laws and features can be identified, learned and implemented in the creation of technologies. Active creative activity in the technologization of education ensures the transition to the implementation of a new paradigm, productivity, creative technologies. In this regard, we believe that pedagogical technology, the content of its concepts, the design algorithm, the result should acquire creative features in order to meet the requirements of modernization of education. This technology makes it possible to make the transition from traditional education to the preparation of a creative personality. To do this, the

conditions, mechanisms and resources that ensure the creativity of a teacher capable of creating and mastering such technologies must change. The goals of education will change from the transfer of ZUN to the formation of readiness for self-knowledge, the essence of education, from the comprehension of well-known patterns, should move into building a world in one's own consciousness, active awareness of oneself in culture, reproductive technologies should be replaced by active, creative ones. We investigated the differences between traditional pedagogical technology and creative technology Types of classes using a creative approach: 1. A lesson with an invitation from a practicing specialist from the field of the subject being studied (for example, when studying topic No. 5 HIV infection, an invitation from a specialist from the Republican AIDS Center) is a form of training that allows students to get closer to the upcoming profession as future specialists. The addition of multimedia slide presentations with materials from WHO, CDC, using slides in English; the use of fragments of video films orient students to their future profession. Advantages: - shows the visibility of the features of the acquired specialty - develops the cognitive abilities of students: attention, observation, thinking, imagination. Disadvantages: - require a lot of preparation- - it is desirable to simultaneously attract a large number of students. 2. Field classes, at the bases of the department, with the involvement of a specialist working in it (for example, when studying the topic of diseases occurring with exanthemes, field classes in the maternity complex, where specialized patients are on inpatient treatment) is an

organizational form of training that allows studying various topics, symptoms and syndromes based on their observation in vivo. Advantages: - establishes a direct and more effective connection of learning with life and the upcoming profession; - affects the emotional sphere; - serves the development of imagination, attention, thinking, speech and memory of students. Disadvantages: - with a significant amount of time spent at the preparatory stage, the relatively small allotted time for independent curation of patients. 3. The lesson-conference is the pedagogical interaction of the teacher and students with maximum independence, activity, initiative of the latter. The conference is usually held with several study groups, under the guidance of their teachers and is aimed at expanding, consolidating and improving knowledge. It is possible to hold a mini-conference within one study group, in this case there is only one leader. Advantages: - develops the creative search of students and teachers; - develops the intellectual abilities of students; - stimulates students' interest in their chosen profession; - develops the ability to work with literature; - promotes the acquisition of the skill to analyze and summarize the results; - free discussion of problematic issues; - the ability to speak to an audience, to present the material competently, forms the ability to identify essential features and properties and convey them to listeners. After distinguishing between the two technologies, we came to the following conclusion. The first reaction of the teacher may well be a complete rejection, rejection of creativity and an innovative approach: this is unrealistic and does not make sense. Let's try to give a kind of "proof against the

contrary". You should immediately pay attention to the fact that in the course of a traditionally conducted lesson there are many difficult moments. The "old", traditional technique is increasingly failing. It is not easy to effectively counter this. So why not look for an alternative? We bring to your attention an example that clearly shows the possibilities of the technology of creativity in teaching a complex and meaningful medical discipline - infectious diseases. Gynecology is an objectively difficult subject, especially for 5th and 6th year students of the Faculty of Medicine. The teacher has to face numerous difficulties and make considerable efforts to achieve very modest results. The main problem, perhaps, is that the study of this discipline with a small number of academic hours involves a large amount of

independent work of students with literature. And these are, as a rule, "heavy" special texts, scientific articles and monographs. When faced with difficulties, some students simply "give up". Others, without even trying to understand, to understand the topic under study, are limited to simple unintelligent memorization (that is, "memorization"). A teacher in such a situation has only to dream about improving the quality of education. When traditional education is so difficult, not every teacher will decide to experiment. First of all, because of the fear that the innovation, which provides students with more "freedom" and independence, will lead to a decrease in the requirements for their knowledge and skills, a drop in discipline in the classroom.

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